

Vorticity-Driven Rotating Universe: A Classical Route to the Hubble Tension and the Dark Sector

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We consider the Euler equations for an incompressible, inviscid cosmic fluid coupled to a Lorentz-like inertial acceleration derived from the gravito-electromagnetic (GEM) formalism of linearized General Relativity. This approximation is valid in the weak-field, large-scale regime appropriate for baryonic flows. A consistent solution for the solenoidal component of the acceleration is interpreted as a cosmic vorticity field $\boldsymbol{\omega}$, reminiscent of Gödel’s rotating Universe, but sourced here by mass currents rather than spacetime geometry. The resulting angular velocity field $\boldsymbol{\Omega}(\mathbf{r}, t)$ links to the Hubble–Lemaître law via Stokes’ theorem and an equivalence between gravitational and transverse Doppler redshifts. Together, these mechanisms support a kinematic reinterpretation of the Hubble parameter H as a space- and time-dependent differential angular velocity. In the pressureless (dust-like) regime, the associated dispersion relation recovers a Friedmann-like structure, reinterpreting the cosmological constant Λ as a *cosmological dispersion parameter* (CDP), linked to the propagation scale and formally superluminal group velocities of collective rotational modes. Rotational dispersion naturally induces a temporal decay of $\boldsymbol{\Omega}(t)$ on Hubble timescales, leading to a gradual reduction in apparent recession velocities. The resulting redshifts arise not from metric expansion but from the transverse motion of the rotating cosmic fluid. As a direct observational signature, the model predicts a negative redshift drift of $\dot{z} \approx -2.54 \times 10^{-10} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ at $z = 2.75$, and a localized positive drift of $\dot{z} \approx +1.69 \times 10^{-12} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ at $z = 7.05$, both within or approaching the sensitivity range of next-generation ultra-stable spectroscopic surveys. This rotational interpretation offers a coherent alternative framework that may contribute to alleviating the current observational tensions associated with the Hubble parameter, while yielding distinctive and falsifiable predictions that differ from those of Λ CDM.

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the most intriguing aspects of modern cosmology, the expansion of the Universe, is mathematically described in General Relativity through the inclusion of a cosmological constant, Λ . This term plays a central role in the Friedmann equations and is typically interpreted as a repulsive form of energy known as dark energy. However, its physical nature remains elusive and has historically been a source of conceptual tension. Interestingly, Einstein originally introduced Λ to obtain a static Universe, later reconsidered its necessity following the discovery of cosmic expansion, and even speculated on its interpretation in terms of negative mass distributions [1]. After the formulation of the Hubble–Lemaître law [2, 3], Λ became an essential component of the standard cosmological model, has long been a source of theoretical controversy.

The Λ CDM model, which combines the cosmological constant with cold dark matter, has been remarkably successful in explaining a wide range of cosmological observations, from the cosmic microwave background to large-

scale structure formation and baryon acoustic oscillations. Importantly, it is rooted in the weak-field limit of General Relativity, where the field equations reduce to an effectively Newtonian form on cosmological scales. Within this framework, both dark matter and dark energy are introduced as effective components to account for observational discrepancies, although their fundamental origin remains unknown.

Among alternative solutions to Einstein’s field equations, several exact models incorporate intrinsic cosmic rotation, such as the Lanczos–van Stockum dust cylinder [4, 5] and Gödel’s Universe [6], where rotation is sustained by a homogeneous matter distribution and a non-zero cosmological constant. Although these models feature non-zero vorticity and exotic properties like closed timelike curves [7, 8], their limited observational viability motivates the search for more realistic rotating cosmologies.

Rotation is a pervasive phenomenon across cosmic structures—from galaxies and clusters to filaments [9], and possibly even imprinted in the cosmic microwave background [10]—suggesting that angular momentum plays a fundamental role in cosmic evolution [11, 12]. In numerical simulations, vorticity has gained relevance in modeling dark matter dynamics [13], many-body gravitational systems [14–17], and baryon–dark matter interactions [18].

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Several mechanisms may have generated vorticity in the early Universe prior to recombination, including anisotropic stress [19], second-order cosmological perturbations [20], primordial magnetic fields and MHD turbulence [21], cosmological phase transitions [22], and baroclinic instabilities [23].

Inspired by Gamow’s early speculation on a rotating Universe [24], it is plausible that primordial vorticity, if present, was transferred to baryonic matter via conservation of angular momentum during recombination, seeding the rotational dynamics observed in galaxies and clusters. Over time, this could manifest as a global, space- and time-dependent differential rotation field $\boldsymbol{\Omega}(\mathbf{r}, t)$, compatible with large-scale structure formation and cosmic anisotropies.

Recent precision measurements of the Hubble parameter have revealed a persistent discrepancy—known as the Hubble tension—between early- and late-time determinations. Direct measurements yield values such as $H_0 = 82.4 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ from strong lensing [25], $H_0 = 74.03 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ from Cepheid-calibrated supernovae [26, 27], and the most precise local estimate $H_0 = 73.04 \pm 1.04 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ from the SH0ES team using HST and Gaia-calibrated Cepheids [28]. In contrast, indirect measurements based on the cosmic microwave background give $H_0 = 67.66 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ [29]. More recently, the DESI Collaboration reported $H_0 = 68.4 \pm 1.0 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ from BAO measurements [30], consistent with CMB estimates but still in tension with local probes. Similarly, the Chicago–Carnegie Hubble Program, combining JWST and HST data, reported a best estimate of $H_0 = 70.39 \pm 1.22 \text{ (stat)} \pm 1.33 \text{ (sys)} \pm 0.70 \text{ (}\sigma_{\text{SN}}\text{) km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ [31], derived from TRGB distances applied to a SN Ia sample and anchored by NGC 4258. This value lies between those from Planck and SH0ES, and agrees within uncertainties with DESI measurements, reinforcing the presence of a smooth trend across redshift. This tension exceeds statistical uncertainty and has motivated proposals ranging from a time-varying Λ [32] to local inhomogeneities [33], modified gravity [34], anisotropy violations [35–37], and systematic calibration errors [38].

In this context, the present paper investigates a classical fluid dynamical reinterpretation of phenomena typically ascribed to dark energy and the Hubble tension, by adopting the gravito-electromagnetic (GEM) approximation to General Relativity in the weak-field regime. We consider the Universe as a rotating baryonic fluid, sustained by primordial vorticity transferred during recombination, and derive a self-consistent angular velocity field $\boldsymbol{\Omega}(\mathbf{r}, t)$. Within this formulation, the cosmological constant emerges naturally as a cosmological dispersion parameter (CDP), reflecting the dispersive propagation of rotational inertial modes. The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: in section II, we introduce the GEM-Euler theoretical framework and derive the dynamical equations governing cosmic vorticity. Section III provides explicit solutions to these equations, obtaining

a time-dependent angular velocity field consistent with observed Hubble values. Section IV establishes a direct correspondence between our rotational framework and traditional cosmology, interpreting dark energy effects as consequences of rotational dispersion. The emergence of large-scale isotropy and homogeneity from local inertial dynamics is demonstrated in section V. Observational predictions, particularly redshift drift as a distinctive signature of cosmic rotation, are developed in section VI. Finally, section VII critically assesses the observational viability, discusses theoretical limits, and highlights directions for future investigations.

II. MODEL AND THEORETICAL FORMALISM

We model the Universe as a classical cosmic fluid with constant baryonic density ρ_b , assumed to be incompressible and inviscid. In this continuum description, the evolution of the velocity field $\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{r}, t)$ is governed by the Euler equations, which express the conservation of linear momentum in the absence of dissipative forces:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v} = -\frac{1}{\rho_b} \nabla P + \mathbf{a}, \quad (1)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} = 0. \quad (2)$$

In Eq. (1), the left-hand side is the material derivative (or convective acceleration), while the right-hand side includes the pressure gradient and the internal acceleration field \mathbf{a} .

To account for the internal inertial effects in a rotating cosmic fluid, we invoke the GEM approximation. This formalism, derived from the linearized Einstein equations, yields a set of equations formally analogous to Maxwell’s:

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{g} = -4\pi G \rho_b, \quad (3)$$

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{g} = -\frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \mathbf{K}}{\partial t}, \quad (4)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{K} = 0, \quad (5)$$

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{K} = -\frac{4\pi G}{c} \mathbf{J}_b + \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \mathbf{g}}{\partial t}. \quad (6)$$

The total acceleration acting on the fluid is then given by

$$\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{g} + \frac{1}{c} \mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{K}, \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{r}, t)$ and $\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{r}, t)$ are the gravitoelectric and gravitomagnetic fields, respectively, and \mathbf{J}_b is the mass current density. These fields are derived from scalar and vector potentials as:

$$\mathbf{g} = -\nabla \Phi - \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \mathbf{A}}{\partial t}, \quad (8)$$

$$\mathbf{K} = \nabla \times \mathbf{A}. \quad (9)$$

Under the Lorenz gauge condition and the weak-field limit of General Relativity, Eqs. (8)–(9) reproduce the full system (3)–(6), with the gravitational potentials playing roles formally analogous to those in electrodynamics.

By substituting Eq. (7) into the Euler equation (1) and taking the curl of both sides, one obtains

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\nabla \times \mathbf{v}) - \nabla \times (\mathbf{v} \times (\nabla \times \mathbf{v})) = -\frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \mathbf{K}}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{c} \nabla \times (\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{K}). \quad (10)$$

A consistent solution to this equation is obtained by identifying the gravitomagnetic field with the negative of the vorticity:

$$\mathbf{K} = -c\boldsymbol{\omega}, \quad (11)$$

which implies that the vector potential is related to the velocity field by $\mathbf{A} = -c\mathbf{v} + \nabla\psi$, up to a gauge transformation. By adopting the gauge $\psi = \text{const.}$, we assign direct physical meaning to the vector potential: it encodes the internal motion of the cosmic fluid, and the gravitomagnetic field becomes proportional to its vorticity.

As in magnetohydrodynamics (MHD), where a conducting fluid interacts with its self-generated magnetic field via the Lorentz force $\mathbf{J} \times \mathbf{B}$, the cosmic fluid experiences an analogous inertial force $\frac{1}{c}\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{K}$, here arising from its internal vorticity.[52] This coupling between flow and induced field leads to a self-consistent dynamical structure.

In Gödel’s rotating Universe [8], all rotating structures, such as galaxies and clusters, contribute to the global vorticity field. However, unlike Gödel’s solution, where rotation is embedded in the spacetime geometry itself, the rotation considered here arises from the physical motion of matter. This distinction leads to a causal and gauge-consistent formulation, in which the vector potential directly encodes the internal dynamics of the cosmic fluid.

Although the vorticity field $\boldsymbol{\omega}$ is solenoidal—implying zero net flux through any closed surface—it may still produce non-zero circulation within bounded regions. In particular, the Observable Universe contains a finite number of rotating structures that sustain localized vorticity, giving rise to measurable circulation. By Stokes’ theorem, the circulation of the velocity field around a closed contour $\partial\Sigma$ is related to the vorticity flux through the enclosed surface Σ :

$$\Gamma = \oint_{\partial\Sigma} \mathbf{v} \cdot d\mathbf{r} = \iint_{\Sigma} \boldsymbol{\omega} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}} d\Sigma. \quad (12)$$

For a steady flow with constant angular velocity $\boldsymbol{\Omega}_0$, the velocity field takes the form $\mathbf{v} = \boldsymbol{\Omega}_0 \times \mathbf{r}$, whose vorticity is $\boldsymbol{\omega} = \nabla \times \mathbf{v} = 2\boldsymbol{\Omega}_0$. Substituting into Eq. (12), the circulation within a surface Σ becomes

$$\Gamma = 2\boldsymbol{\Omega}_0 \Sigma, \quad (13)$$

where Σ is the area enclosed by the contour $\partial\Sigma$ and perpendicular to $\boldsymbol{\Omega}_0$. In the equatorial plane, the tangential speed along a circular path is then $v = \Gamma/(2\pi r) = \Omega_0 r$, exhibiting a linear dependence on radius.

This relation mirrors Hubble’s law $v_{\text{rec}} = H_0 D$, with the formal analogy $\Omega_0 \sim H_0$. However, while the Hubble flow describes radial recession due to spacetime expansion, the present scenario corresponds to transverse motion driven by cosmic rotation. Crucially, this rotational motion arises from the dynamical properties of the cosmic fluid itself, not from an expanding metric, and may account for similar observational signatures within the Observable Universe.

The analogy is further reinforced by comparing two distinct relativistic mechanisms that produce redshift. The first is the *gravitational redshift* arising in a static, spherically symmetric mass distribution of uniform density ρ , as predicted by General Relativity. The second is the *transverse Doppler shift* in Special Relativity, experienced by a source moving perpendicular to the line of sight with velocity v_{\perp} . Despite their different origins, both yield identical observational signatures and take the form:

$$1 + z = \left(1 - \frac{8\pi G \rho r^2}{3c^2}\right)^{-1/2} \leftrightarrow 1 + z = \left(1 - \frac{v_{\perp}^2}{c^2}\right)^{-1/2}. \quad (14)$$

Identifying $v_{\perp} = \Omega_0 r$, the expressions become equivalent if

$$\rho = \frac{3\Omega_0^2}{8\pi G}, \quad (15)$$

which coincides with the critical density $\rho_c = 3H_0^2/8\pi G$ in FLRW cosmology when $\Omega_0 = H_0$. This correspondence suggests that cosmic redshift may not necessarily require spacetime expansion: it could instead emerge from relativistic effects associated with large-scale transverse motion.

While gravitational redshift and Doppler shift arise in different physical contexts—curved spacetime versus kinematic motion—their formal similarity at a given radius offers a compelling heuristic. It implies that the Hubble flow may be effectively reproduced by a global vortical structure, where the angular velocity Ω_0 replaces H_0 as the fundamental parameter regulating redshift. The equivalence between the two expressions in Eq. (14) holds exactly under the identification $v_{\perp} = \Omega_0 r$, independent of the velocity scale. For small velocities $v \ll c$, both forms reduce to the same quadratic approximation $z \approx v^2/(2c^2)$, further reinforcing the analogy in the low-redshift regime.

This formal equivalence between gravitational and kinematic redshift reflects a manifestation of the Strong Equivalence Principle (SEP) at cosmological scales. In this framework, observational effects typically attributed to spacetime curvature induced by mass can be effectively mimicked by coherent transverse motion. From an observational standpoint, the origin of redshift—whether

due to a gravitational potential or differential rotation—becomes empirically indistinguishable, provided that the underlying density and velocity profiles are matched. This reinterpretation opens a new pathway to account for cosmic acceleration through inertial dynamics alone, without invoking spacetime expansion or dark energy.

Observational bounds further support this scenario. Simulations of the non-integrated Sachs–Wolfe effect in the CMB constrain any large-scale rotation to below 10^{-9} rad/yr [41], still about an order of magnitude above the observed Hubble parameter $H_0 \sim 7 \times 10^{-11}$ rad/yr. This opens the possibility that a hidden vortical structure underlies the observed redshift–distance relation. A recent independent study by Szigeti *et al.* [42] arrives at a similar conclusion: by introducing a Gödel-inspired, slowly rotating dark-fluid variant of the concordance model, they show that the Hubble tension can be resolved without invoking metric expansion. In their approach, the variation in the Hubble parameter emerges from a decaying angular velocity field, with present-day value $\Omega_0^{\text{dark}} \approx 2 \times 10^{-12}$ rad/yr. Although the model recovers an effective scale factor $a(t)$, it arises dynamically from the underlying matter flow in physical coordinates, rather than being prescribed by the geometry of spacetime.

We now extend the previous analysis to space- and time-dependent vorticity fields $\boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{r}, t)$. Starting from the gravitoelectromagnetic formulation, we take the curl of the Ampère–Maxwell equation (6) and apply the vector identity $\nabla \times (\nabla \times \mathbf{K}) = \nabla(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{K}) - \nabla^2 \mathbf{K}$, along with the solenoidal condition $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{K} = 0$ from Eq. (5). This yields the wave equation:

$$-\nabla^2 \mathbf{K} = -\frac{4\pi G}{c} \nabla \times (\rho_b \mathbf{v}) - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{K}}{\partial t^2}. \quad (16)$$

Assuming a constant baryonic density ρ_b , the current term simplifies to $\nabla \times (\rho_b \mathbf{v}) = \rho_b \boldsymbol{\omega}$. Substituting Eq. (11) into Eq. (16), we obtain the dynamical equation:

$$(\square + \Lambda_b) \boldsymbol{\omega} = 0, \quad (17)$$

where

$$\Lambda_b := \frac{4\pi G \rho_b}{c^2}, \quad (18)$$

and \square is the d'Alembert operator. This is a Klein–Gordon-type equation for the vorticity field, in which the baryonic density acts as an effective mass term. The corresponding dispersion relation,

$$\omega_0^2 = c^2 k^2 - c^2 \Lambda_b, \quad (19)$$

describes the propagation of rotational modes within the cosmic fluid. Interestingly, a similar relation appears in Gödel's rotating Universe, where the angular velocity satisfies $\Omega^2 = 4\pi G \rho_b$ [6], which corresponds to the static limit of Eq. (19) when $k = 0$.

This formulation assumes a constant baryonic density ρ_b , consistent with the Cosmological Principle at large

scales. As will be discussed in the next section, the solutions to Eq. (17) exhibit a finite coherence scale, ensuring that small-scale inhomogeneities are dynamically averaged out. This justifies the use of a homogeneous Klein–Gordon equation to describe the large-scale evolution of $\boldsymbol{\omega}$, and sets the stage for a cosmological model driven by rotational dynamics rather than metric expansion.

III. SOLUTION TO VORTICITY WAVE AND HUBBLE FUNCTION

We propose that the large-scale dynamics of the Universe are governed by the evolution of a cosmic vorticity field, which naturally gives rise to a time-dependent angular velocity field $\boldsymbol{\Omega}(\mathbf{r}, t)$ and an associated cosmological acceleration scale.

To investigate its implications, we analyze the Klein–Gordon-type wave equation for vorticity derived earlier, Eq. (17), with mass term Λ_b proportional to the baryonic density.

Adopting cylindrical coordinates due to expected axial symmetry, and assuming the vorticity field is aligned with the z -axis, we write $\boldsymbol{\omega} = \omega(r, \phi, z, t) \hat{\mathbf{z}}$. The equation becomes:

$$\left[\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \phi^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2} - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} + \Lambda_b \right] \omega = 0. \quad (20)$$

Assuming a separable solution $\omega(r, \phi, z, t) = R(r) \Phi(\phi) Z(z) T(t)$ and dividing Eq. (20) by $R\Phi ZT$, we obtain the following separation equation:

$$\frac{1}{Rr} \frac{d}{dr} \left(r \frac{dR}{dr} \right) + \frac{1}{\Phi r^2} \frac{d^2 \Phi}{d\phi^2} + \frac{1}{Z} \frac{d^2 Z}{dz^2} = \frac{1}{c^2 T} \frac{d^2 T}{dt^2} - \Lambda_b. \quad (21)$$

Each derivative term can be coupled to a constant, such that the temporal equation remain as

$$\frac{d^2 T}{dt^2} + (k^2 c^2 - \Lambda_b c^2) T = 0, \quad (22)$$

whose solution is

$$T(t) = A \cos(\omega_0 t) + B \sin(\omega_0 t), \quad (23)$$

with dispersion relation $\omega_0^2 = c^2 k^2 - c^2 \Lambda_b$.

This oscillatory regime holds when $k^2 > \Lambda_b$; otherwise, the time dependence becomes exponential, leading to hyperbolic solutions possibly associated with instability or decay. Here, we focus on the oscillatory regime.

For the z -dependence, introducing a constant a^2 , one obtain:

$$\frac{d^2 Z}{dz^2} + (k^2 - a^2) Z = 0, \quad (24)$$

with solution

$$Z(z) = C \cos\left(\sqrt{k^2 - a^2} z\right) + D \sin\left(\sqrt{k^2 - a^2} z\right). \quad (25)$$

The angular part is assumed to satisfy:

$$\frac{d^2\Phi}{d\phi^2} + b^2\Phi = 0, \quad (26)$$

with solution

$$\Phi(\phi) = E \cos(b\phi) + F \sin(b\phi). \quad (27)$$

Imposing single-valuedness, $\Phi(\phi + 2\pi) = \Phi(\phi)$, requires $b = n \in \mathbb{Z}$.

Replacing (22), (24) and (26) into (21), the radial equation reduces to the standard Bessel form:

$$r^2 \frac{d^2 R}{dr^2} + r \frac{dR}{dr} + [(ar)^2 - n^2] R = 0, \quad (28)$$

whose regular solutions at the origin are given by:

$$R(r) = J_n(ar), \quad (29)$$

with J_n the Bessel function of the first kind.

Setting $a = k$ and $n = 0$, the solution reduces to

$$\omega(r, t) = [\Omega_e \cos(\omega_0 t) + \Omega_l \sin(\omega_0 t)] J_0(kr), \quad (30)$$

where Ω_e and Ω_l are constants fixed by cosmological boundary conditions expressed in cosmological units (e.g., $\text{km s}^{-1} \text{Mpc}^{-1}$).

To obtain the angular velocity field $\boldsymbol{\Omega}(r, t)$, we use the identity valid under axial symmetry:

$$\boldsymbol{\omega} = \nabla \times (\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{r}) = \left(2\Omega + r \frac{d\Omega}{dr}\right) \hat{\mathbf{z}}. \quad (31)$$

Solving Eq. (31) yields:

$$\boldsymbol{\Omega}(r, t) = [\Omega_e \cos(\omega_0 t) + \Omega_l \sin(\omega_0 t)] \frac{J_1(kr)}{kr} \hat{\mathbf{z}}, \quad (32)$$

where J_1 is the Bessel function of the first kind of order one.

The wave number k in Eq. (32) determines the spatial structure of the angular velocity field $\boldsymbol{\Omega}(r, t)$, with the first zero of the Bessel function $J_1(kr)$ defining a characteristic coherence radius $r_c \sim 3.83/k$. Adopting the dispersion parameter $k = \sqrt{\Lambda}$ from Table I, we obtain

$$r_c = \frac{3.83}{k} \approx \frac{3.83}{\sqrt{\Lambda}} \approx 3.64 \times 10^{26} \text{ m}, \quad (33)$$

a value remarkably close to the comoving radius of the observable Universe, $R_{\text{obs}} \approx 4.4 \times 10^{26} \text{ m}$ in standard cosmology. This suggests that the coherence length r_c , associated with differential rotation, plays a dynamical role analogous to a causal horizon: it sets the spatial scale beyond which the oscillatory modes of $\boldsymbol{\Omega}(r, t)$ lose phase

coherence, effectively suppressing net rotational acceleration. In this view, r_c defines a natural boundary for the vorticity-induced structure of the cosmic fluid. Its vast scale also lends support to the assumption of constant baryonic density adopted earlier, since fluctuations below r_c are dynamically smoothed by the coherence of rotational modes.

The group velocity of these modes,

$$v_g = \frac{\partial \omega_0}{\partial k} = \frac{c^2 k}{\omega_0} \approx 3.05 \times 10^8 \text{ m/s}, \quad (34)$$

is formally superluminal, reflecting the non-causal nature of collective inertial coherence. Although $v_g > c$, this does not imply any transfer of information faster than light. Instead, it governs the spatial extent of coherent rotation, reinforcing the interpretation of r_c as the maximal scale of vorticity order.

To calibrate the model with cosmological observations, we impose that the angular velocity field $\boldsymbol{\Omega}(r, t)$ reproduces the observed Hubble parameter at two distinct epochs. Specifically, we require $\Omega(r_U, t_e) = 67.66 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{Mpc}^{-1}$ in the early Universe and $\Omega(r_l, t_l) = 73.24 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{Mpc}^{-1}$ in the local Universe, as summarized in Table I. These observational constraints determine the amplitudes of the angular velocity wave as $\Omega_e = 183.47 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{Mpc}^{-1}$ and $\Omega_l = 54.41 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{Mpc}^{-1}$, defined over the model's full timespan $T_f = 15.27 \text{ Gyr}$.

Table I summarizes the numerical values adopted throughout this section. The top portion lists standard cosmological parameters from the Planck 2018 results [29], while the bottom portion presents the calibrated quantities from the proposed rotational framework. These include the early and late angular velocities, baryonic density, and effective dispersion parameters governing the propagation of vorticity waves. The values for Ω_e and Ω_l are chosen to match the early and late Hubble parameters, ensuring observational consistency in the context of inertial cosmology.

In this framework, the present kinematic radius of the observable Universe is fixed as $r_U = 1.44 \times 10^{26} \text{ m}$ for calculations. All fundamental quantities used in the model—including densities, velocities, and wave parameters—are listed in Table I. The function $\boldsymbol{\Omega}(r, t)$, expressed in cosmological units, governs the spatial and temporal variation of recession rates, effectively replacing the Hubble parameter with a dynamical quantity.

Figures 1–4 illustrate the evolution of $\boldsymbol{\Omega}(r, t)$ at four cosmological epochs, from the early Universe to a future reversal phase within r_U . Each panel is centered on the observer, with the outer edge marking the causal horizon at the corresponding time t_U . The calibrated oscillatory behavior of $\boldsymbol{\Omega}$ not only matches observational Hubble values but also accounts dynamically for the Hubble tension, as regions emitting light at earlier times naturally exhibit higher effective values.

At early times (Fig. 1), $\boldsymbol{\Omega}$ is nearly uniform near the horizon, ranging from 64 to 69 $\text{km s}^{-1} \text{Mpc}^{-1}$, consistent with CMB-inferred Hubble values. By $t \approx$

Tabela I: Cosmological parameters from the Planck 2018 results [29]. The top section presents standard cosmological values, while the bottom section shows the parameters obtained from the present model.

Description	Symbol	Value	Unit
Standard cosmology (Planck 2018)			
Matter density parameter (total)	Ω_m	0.3111 ± 0.0056	–
Baryon density parameter	Ω_b	0.04897 ± 0.00031	–
Dark energy density parameter	Ω_Λ	0.6889 ± 0.0056	–
Critical density	ρ_c	8.53×10^{-27}	kg m^{-3}
Age of the Universe	t_{age}	13.787 ± 0.020	Gyr
Hubble parameter (early Universe [29])	H_0	67.66 ± 0.42	$\text{km s}^{-1} \text{Mpc}^{-1}$
Hubble parameter (late Universe [28])	H_l	73.24 ± 1.74	$\text{km s}^{-1} \text{Mpc}^{-1}$
Speed of light	c	2.99792×10^8	m s^{-1}
Gravitational constant	G	6.67×10^{-11}	$\text{m}^3 \text{kg}^{-1} \text{s}^{-2}$
Parameters from the proposed model			
Reference early time	t_e	0	s
Reference late time	t_l	3.02×10^{17}	s
Time since the Big Bang	t_U	4.81×10^{17}	s
Apparent Radius of the observable Universe	r_U	1.44×10^{26}	m
Radius of H_l measurement region	r_l	5.38×10^{25}	m
Coherence Radius of Ω wave	r_c	3.64×10^{26}	m
Baryonic density	ρ_b	4.2113×10^{-28}	kg m^{-3}
Baryonic parameter	Λ_b	3.9299×10^{-54}	m^{-2}
Cosmological Dispersion Parameter (CDP)	Λ	1.1092×10^{-52}	m^{-2}
Early angular velocity	Ω_e	183.47	$\text{km s}^{-1} \text{Mpc}^{-1}$
Late angular velocity	Ω_l	54.41	$\text{km s}^{-1} \text{Mpc}^{-1}$
Phase velocity of Ω wave	v_p	2.94434×10^8	m s^{-1}
Group velocity of Ω wave	v_g	3.05249×10^8	m s^{-1}

Figure 1: Density plot of $\Omega(r, t)$ in $\text{km}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}\cdot\text{Mpc}^{-1}$ at the origin of cosmic time.

Figure 2: Density plot of $\Omega(r, t)$ in $\text{km}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}\cdot\text{Mpc}^{-1}$ at $t \approx 2.95$ Gyr.

2.95 Gy (Fig. 2), the angular velocity rises above $80 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{Mpc}^{-1}$ in the central region, marking a temporary increase before the long-term decay sets in. This early growth phase suggests an epoch of enhanced rotational coherence, which—unlike in ΛCDM —could mani-

fest observationally as a *positive redshift drift* at high z . The resulting spatial gradient in Ω illustrates the model's core mechanism: observations from different emission times naturally yield different expansion rates.

At $t \approx 9.62$ Gy (Fig. 3), corresponding to a recent

Figure 3: Density plot of $\Omega(r, t)$ in $\text{km}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}\cdot\text{Mpc}^{-1}$ at $t \approx 9.62$ Gyr, corresponding to the observationally inferred local Hubble rate.

epoch prior to the present, the angular velocity has dropped to $\sim 73 \text{ km}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}\cdot\text{Mpc}^{-1}$ near the center, reflecting large-scale dispersion of rotational energy. The profile becomes smoother, indicating a reduction in rotational gradients.

In the future ($t \approx 19.1$ Gy, Fig. 4), the central region exhibits a sign reversal in Ω , indicating a transition to retrograde motion. This inversion results from the natural temporal oscillation in the angular velocity field and reflects the cyclic behavior inherent to the Euler–GEM dynamics. Unlike the spatial loss of phase coherence beyond r_c , this time-dependent reversal maintains global coherence and reveals the periodic structure of the rotational flow.

Together, these snapshots illustrate how $\Omega(r, t)$ evolves both radially and temporally, offering a dynamical explanation for cosmic acceleration. Rather than postulating dark energy, the model attributes the observed variation in H_0 to the decline of Ω at fixed positions. Regions emitting light in the past exhibit higher apparent expansion rates, naturally reproducing the Hubble tension as a differential inertial effect.

Figure 5 shows the tangential velocity $v = |\mathbf{\Omega}(r, t) \times \mathbf{r}|$, normalized by the speed of light, for selected cosmic times. The solid colored curves correspond to specific epochs in the evolution of the angular velocity field: the CMB time in this model ($t = 0$), an early maximum of Ω ($t \approx 2.95$ Gyr, red curve), the local Hubble determination epoch ($t \approx 9.62$ Gyr), a more recent past ($t \approx 12.2$ Gyr), and the present time ($t = 15.3$ Gyr). For comparison, the dashed black line shows the standard Hubble–Lemaître velocity, the dashed gray line marks the speed of light, and the dotted vertical line indicates the present-day observational horizon r_U .

As the Universe evolves, the rotational profiles shift downward, reflecting the decay of $\Omega(r, t)$ over time. The

Figure 4: Density plot of $\Omega(r, t)$ in $\text{km}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}\cdot\text{Mpc}^{-1}$ at $t \approx 19.09$ Gyr, in a future epoch beyond the current age of the Universe.

Figure 5: Tangential velocity $v/c = |\mathbf{\Omega}(r, t) \times \mathbf{r}|/c$ as a function of radial distance, plotted on a log-linear scale for five distinct cosmic times. The dashed black line represents the standard Hubble–Lemaître velocity, while the dashed gray line corresponds to the light speed limit. A vertical dotted line marks the apparent observational horizon $r_U \approx 1.44 \times 10^{26}$ m. The red curve ($t \approx 2.95$ Gyr) highlights the early maximum of Ω , which corresponds to an epoch of apparent acceleration.

red curve reveals a brief initial phase in which Ω increases, resulting in velocities that exceed the standard Hubble flow across a wide radial range. This transient behavior can be interpreted as an early phase of apparent acceleration, consistent with a positive redshift drift at high z in this model. Subsequently, the intersection point with the Hubble–Lemaître curve moves inward, indicating that the spatial scale at which rotation mimics expansion becomes smaller. This explains why local measurements at later times yield higher effective Hubble

values: they correspond to light emitted in the past, when Ω was intrinsically larger. Although the plot extends beyond the observational horizon r_U , it reveals that the rotational velocity converges asymptotically toward the Hubble flow, supporting the model's consistency with large-scale cosmological observations in the recent epoch.

It is worth noting that the angular velocity profile $\Omega(r, t)$ decays smoothly beyond the present horizon r_U , approaching zero near the coherence radius r_c . This behavior implies that, despite the apparent kinematic limit at r_U , regions beyond this radius may still be observable due to the decreasing recession velocity at larger scales. However, around r_U itself, the recession speed reaches or slightly exceeds the speed of light, creating a narrow observational gap or *dark shell* in the present epoch. This shell separates the nearby luminous Universe from more distant regions that, paradoxically, may remain within observational reach due to the dispersive structure of the velocity field.

IV. CONTACT WITH TRADITIONAL COSMOLOGY AND INTERPRETATION OF DARK ENERGY

To connect the results of the previous section with standard Friedmann cosmology, we recall the dispersion relation obtained in Eq. (19). By identifying $\omega_0^2 \equiv -\nabla^2 \Phi_{\text{eff}}$ and setting $k^2 \equiv \Lambda$, this relation can be reinterpreted as a modified Poisson equation for gravity in terms of an effective potential:[53]

$$\nabla^2 \Phi_{\text{eff}} = c^2(\Lambda_b - \Lambda). \quad (35)$$

Assuming cylindrical symmetry, the general solution to Eq. (35) becomes:

$$\Phi_{\text{eff}}(r) = \pi G \rho_b r^2 - \frac{1}{4} \Lambda c^2 r^2, \quad (36)$$

which recovers the classical Newtonian potential when rotational dispersion vanishes, i.e., $\Lambda = 0$. The second term arises from the dispersion parameter Λ , introduced in the Klein–Gordon equation for vorticity. It reflects the large-scale diffusive behavior of rotational modes and acts as a repulsive potential growing with r^2 . Although derived from an inertial fluid description, this term mimics a centrifugal-like effect: it counteracts gravity and induces large-scale acceleration without invoking dark energy as a separate component. This functional structure is reminiscent of the potential obtained in the Newtonian limit of General Relativity with a cosmological constant [1], where a $-\Lambda c^2 r^2/6$ term appears. While the mathematical form is similar, the physical origin here lies in the dispersive dynamics of rotational modes rather than in vacuum energy or geometric curvature.

To further relate this framework to fluid dynamics, we rewrite the Euler equation (1) using the scalar and vector

potentials from Eqs. (8) and (9):

$$\frac{d\mathbf{v}}{dt} = -\frac{1}{\rho_b} \nabla P - \nabla \Phi_{\text{eff}} - \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \mathbf{A}}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{c} \mathbf{v} \times (\nabla \times \mathbf{A}), \quad (37)$$

and by substituting $\mathbf{A} = -c\mathbf{v}$, Eq. (37) simplifies to:

$$\frac{d\mathbf{v}}{dt} = -\frac{1}{\rho_b} \nabla P - \nabla \Phi_{\text{eff}} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} - \mathbf{v} \times (\nabla \times \mathbf{v}). \quad (38)$$

Assuming a rotating fluid with $\mathbf{v} = \boldsymbol{\Omega}(r, t) \times \mathbf{r}$, and rearranging the material derivative accordingly, one obtains a Bernoulli-like expression:

$$\nabla \Phi_{\text{eff}} + \frac{1}{\rho_b} \nabla P + \frac{1}{2} \nabla (\Omega^2 r^2) = 0. \quad (39)$$

This relation remains valid even in the presence of rotational dispersion, since the assumptions of incompressibility and inviscid flow are preserved. The combined effects of gravity, rotation, and wave dispersion are all encoded in Eq. (39). It is therefore natural to define the gradient of an effective pressure function:

$$\nabla \mathcal{P} = 0, \quad (40)$$

where the effective pressure $\mathcal{P}(r, t)$ is defined as

$$\mathcal{P}(r, t) = P + \rho_b \left(\pi G \rho_b r^2 - \frac{1}{4} \Lambda c^2 r^2 + \frac{1}{2} \Omega^2 r^2 \right). \quad (41)$$

Here, \mathcal{P} represents the sum of the mechanical pressure P , the gravitational potential energy density, a rotational (gravitomagnetic) contribution proportional to Ω^2 , and a dispersive term governed by the dispersion parameter Λ . Under the assumptions of an incompressible and inviscid fluid, \mathcal{P} must remain spatially constant. However, the mechanical pressure P itself may still vary with position and time to locally balance gravitational attraction, rotational support, and dispersive effects encoded in the effective potential Φ_{eff} .

To establish a direct connection with the standard cosmological model, consider the limiting case of quasi-rigid rotation with $\Omega = H_0$ (the Hubble parameter inferred from CMB observations) and adopt the dust approximation ($P = 0$). In this regime, Eq. (40) simplifies to:

$$\Lambda = \frac{2}{c^2} (H_0^2 + 2\pi G \rho_b) = 1.1092 \times 10^{-52} \text{ m}^{-2}, \quad (42)$$

which closely matches the cosmological constant inferred from the Λ CDM model:

$$\Lambda_{\text{CDM}} = 3 \left(\frac{H_0}{c} \right)^2 \Omega_{\Lambda} = 1.1056 \times 10^{-52} \text{ m}^{-2}. \quad (43)$$

This correspondence suggests that the cosmological constant may be reinterpreted as a *cosmological dispersion parameter* (CDP), arising from the combined contributions of rotational support and gravitational self-attraction in a purely baryonic cosmic fluid. Notably, the three terms contributing to the effective pressure—gravitational attraction ($\sim G\rho_b^2$), rotational inertia ($\sim \Omega^2$), and dispersive repulsion ($\sim \Lambda$)—naturally

echo the roles played by baryonic matter, dark matter, and dark energy in the Λ CDM model.

Figure 6 illustrates the evolution of the effective pressure $\mathcal{P}(r, t)$, defined in Eq. (41), under the dust approximation ($P = 0$). At early times, \mathcal{P} remains positive across all relevant spatial scales. Around $t \approx 2.95$ Gyr (red curve), the pressure exhibits a distinct maximum in the outer regions, near the cosmological horizon. This reflects an epoch of enhanced inward inertial stress, where the rotational support temporarily dominates the dispersive term, leading to a brief phase of effective attraction on large scales.

As the Universe evolves, the dispersive term proportional to Λ becomes dominant at large radii, progressively shifting \mathcal{P} toward negative values in the outer regions. This transition marks the emergence of a repulsive regime driven by rotational dispersion.

Figure 6: Effective pressure $\mathcal{P}(r, t)$ under the dust approximation ($P = 0$) for different cosmic epochs. Each curve corresponds to a fixed time since the Big Bang. The red curve ($t \approx 2.95$ Gyr) exhibits a prominent maximum in the outer regions, indicating strong inward inertial pressure before dispersion dominates. The purple curve represents the present epoch. The spatial profiles reveal a transition from inward effective pressure to outward repulsion, governed by the increasing influence of the cosmological dispersion parameter Λ .

Although $\mathcal{P}(P = 0)$ would be spatially uniform in a strictly incompressible, inviscid fluid, the presence of gradients in the effective potential and the rotating flow structure induces a residual spatial profile. This behavior emulates the effect of a cosmological pressure term in Friedmann models, despite arising here from purely classical dynamics.

In this light, the cosmological constant—often introduced as an exotic energy component with negative pressure—may instead reflect the behavior of a rotating baryonic fluid. Rather than invoking new physics, the apparent acceleration could stem from inertial stresses and spatial pressure gradients intrinsic to the rotating baryonic fluid, which are usually neglected in conventional cosmological frameworks.

To assess the dynamical impact of differential rotation—characterized by the time- and space-dependent angular velocity field $\Omega(r, t)$ from Eq. (32)—we evaluate the gradient of the effective pressure to extract the total acceleration field:

$$\frac{1}{\rho_b} \nabla P + 2\pi G \rho_b r \hat{r} - \frac{1}{2} \Lambda c^2 r \hat{r} + \frac{1}{2} \nabla(\Omega^2 r^2) = 0, \quad (44)$$

and define:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{\rho_b} \nabla P &\equiv \mathbf{a}_{\text{tot}}(r, t) \\ &= -2\pi G \rho_b r \hat{r} + \frac{1}{2} \Lambda c^2 r \hat{r} - \frac{1}{2} \nabla(\Omega^2 r^2). \end{aligned} \quad (45)$$

The first term is the standard gravitational attraction, the second introduces a repulsive contribution from the dispersion parameter Λ , and the third term arises from the rotational (gravitomagnetic) gradient of $\Omega(r, t)$. At small scales, the Newtonian and rotational terms dominate; at large scales, the dispersive term prevails. Importantly, the rotational term governed by the gradient of $\Omega^2 r^2$ plays a role analogous to that of dark matter in standard cosmology: it provides additional centripetal acceleration that counteracts the deficit left by visible matter alone. Thus, in this framework, what is commonly attributed to the presence of dark matter emerges naturally from the inertial structure of the cosmic fluid—specifically, from large-scale coherent rotation. The time evolution of Ω modulates the third term, introducing cyclic features into the total acceleration.

Figure 7: Radial profiles of the total effective acceleration $\mathbf{a}_{\text{tot}}(r, t)$ and its physical components for two cosmological epochs: the early Universe ($t = 0$) and the present epoch ($t = t_U$). The gravitational (blue), dispersive (red), rotational (green), and total (purple) accelerations are shown. While gravity and dispersion are time-independent, the rotational and total curves evolve over time.

Figure 7 highlights how \mathbf{a}_{tot} evolves with time and scale. In the early Universe, differential rotation reinforces attraction across all radii, consistent with a decelerated phase. As time progresses, the rotational support diminishes, and the repulsive effect of the dispersion

parameter becomes more prominent at intermediate and large scales. This evolution is not externally imposed, but rather emerges from the dynamics of $\Omega(r, t)$, governed by the dispersion relation (19). The CDP thus encapsulates a natural, scale-dependent transition from attractive to repulsive regimes, rooted in the inertial structure of the cosmic fluid. Crucially, in this context, the rotational term fulfills the dynamical role that is conventionally ascribed to dark matter, providing the additional acceleration necessary to explain observed dynamics without invoking non-baryonic matter.

V. EMERGENT ISOTROPY AND THE OBSERVATIONAL AMBIGUITY OF THE ROTATION AXIS

In the cosmological scenario of a rotating cosmic fluid, it might seem intuitive to question the existence of a privileged rotation axis. However, within the framework developed in this work, this concern proves to be merely formal. While previous sections have addressed the global rotational dynamics of the cosmic fluid, this section investigates how such rotation is locally perceived by a co-rotating observer. Specifically, we explore conditions under which local variations in the angular velocity and thus the local Hubble parameter are negligible. *We demonstrate that under quasi-rigid rotation, observational consequences naturally appear isotropic and homogeneous at cosmologically relevant scales, ensuring compatibility with the Cosmological Principle.*

Given the vast temporal and spatial scales characterizing the observable Universe, consider an observer moving from an initial radial position r (perpendicular to the primary axis of rotation) to another position r' . Locally, the cosmic fluid velocity transforms according to

$$\mathbf{v} \rightarrow \mathbf{v} + \boldsymbol{\Omega}(\mathbf{r}', t) \times \mathbf{r}', \quad (46)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\Omega}(\mathbf{r}', t)$ is the local angular velocity. In this non-inertial reference frame, the Euler equation becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v} &= -\frac{1}{\rho} \nabla p' - \nabla \phi' - \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \mathbf{A}'}{\partial t} \\ &+ \frac{1}{c} \mathbf{v} \times (\nabla \times \mathbf{A}') - 2\boldsymbol{\Omega}(\mathbf{r}', t) \times \mathbf{v} \\ &- \boldsymbol{\Omega}(\mathbf{r}', t) \times [\boldsymbol{\Omega}(\mathbf{r}', t) \times \mathbf{r}'] - \frac{d\boldsymbol{\Omega}(\mathbf{r}', t)}{dt} \times \mathbf{r}'. \end{aligned} \quad (47)$$

The last three terms represent the Coriolis, centrifugal, and Euler inertial accelerations, respectively.

Under the assumption of quasi-rigid rotation, the angular velocity field is spatially uniform and stationary: $\boldsymbol{\Omega}(\mathbf{r}', t) = \boldsymbol{\Omega}_0 = \text{const.}$ Consequently, the velocity field simplifies to $\mathbf{v} = \boldsymbol{\Omega}_0 \times \mathbf{r}'$. In this regime, all explicit time dependencies vanish since $\partial_t \mathbf{v} = 0$, $\partial_t \mathbf{A}' = 0$, and

$d_t \boldsymbol{\Omega}_0 = 0$. Thus, the Euler equation (47) reduces to:

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v} &= -\frac{1}{\rho} \nabla p' - \nabla \phi' \\ &- 2\boldsymbol{\Omega}_0 \times \mathbf{v} + \frac{1}{c} \mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{K}' + \nabla \left(\frac{1}{2} \Omega_0^2 r'^2 \right). \end{aligned} \quad (48)$$

If the gravitomagnetic field \mathbf{K}' satisfies condition (11), specifically $\mathbf{K}' = -2c \boldsymbol{\Omega}_0$, the Coriolis force is exactly balanced by this induced field. Consequently, the equation simplifies further to:

$$(\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v} = -\nabla \Phi', \quad (49)$$

where Φ' incorporates gravitational, pressure, and centrifugal contributions. This form clearly shows that inertial effects are entirely encapsulated in a scalar potential Φ' , leaving no explicit inertial vector $\boldsymbol{\Omega}_0$ within the equation. The fluid acceleration manifests solely through streamline curvature, represented by the convective derivative term.

Thus, when transitioning radially from r to r' , the observer's trajectory smoothly integrates the centrifugal potential $\frac{1}{2} \Omega_0^2 r'^2$ into Φ' . The observer's path follows the flow curvature, analogous to a reversed Coriolis trajectory, ensuring continuous co-rotation with the local fluid frame. Importantly, as the cosmological radius of curvature is extremely large, the local motion closely approximates uniform rectilinear motion with negligible centrifugal acceleration.

In this scenario, assuming a constant mass density and radial distances $r < r_c$, all co-rotating observers experience identical inertial conditions, perceiving themselves as centrally located. Crucially, the axis of rotation itself becomes observationally ambiguous: despite the global presence of rotation, it cannot be locally inferred from the dynamics. Because equation (49) contains no explicit directional vectors and describes forces purely through the gradient of a scalar potential, no preferential direction emerges from local dynamics. Consequently, observational isotropy and an effective form of homogeneity emerge dynamically at large scales, fully consistent with the Cosmological Principle within the coherence domain of rotation.

VI. REDSHIFT DRIFT AS A TEST OF THE ROTATIONAL FRAMEWORK

In standard cosmology, the redshift drift quantifies the temporal change in the redshift of distant sources as a direct probe of the Universe's expansion dynamics [46, 47]. In our model, where large-scale behavior is governed by the cosmic angular velocity field (32), the redshift has a purely kinematic origin and arises from the differential rotation of the cosmic fluid. In this context, the temporal and spatial evolution of Ω effectively replaces the Hubble parameter as the regulator of apparent recession rates.

Under the assumption of a stationary gravitational potential and constant matter density, this redshift may also be interpreted as a gravitational shift. These two perspectives are heuristically equivalent, as shown by Eq. (14), which leads to the density–rotation relation in Eq. (15).

In the relativistic regime, the transverse Doppler redshift for a source moving tangentially with velocity $v = r\Omega(r, t)$ is given by:

$$1 + z(t) = \left(1 - \frac{r^2\Omega^2(r, t)}{c^2}\right)^{-1/2}, \quad (50)$$

which remains valid for arbitrary subluminal velocities $v < c$. This expression forms the basis for computing the redshift drift:

$$\frac{dz}{dt} = \frac{r^2\Omega(r, t)}{c^2 \left(1 - \frac{r^2\Omega^2(r, t)}{c^2}\right)^{3/2}} \cdot \frac{\partial\Omega(r, t)}{\partial t}. \quad (51)$$

In this framework, the measured redshift drift corresponds to the temporal variation of the transverse velocity $v = r\Omega(r, t)$ at the location of the absorbing cloud. That is, the quantity dz/dt reflects how the angular velocity of the cosmic fluid is evolving over time at the coordinates of absorption—not at the source of emission. This is fundamentally distinct from the standard interpretation, where redshift drift probes the integrated variation of the expansion rate along the light path to the emitter.

This distinction leads to a unique observational signature. While Λ CDM predicts a *positive drift* at low redshift due to late-time acceleration and a *negative drift* at high redshift due to earlier deceleration, the rotational model instead predicts a *consistently negative drift* over most of the observational range. This reflects a Universe that is dynamically decelerating due to the decay of the rotation rate. Only at very early times (corresponding to extremely high redshifts) does the model admit a brief phase of increasing angular velocity, resulting in a localized region of *positive drift*.

Using the angular velocity field defined in Eq. (32), we numerically compute the redshift drift at three representative redshifts, aligned with well-characterized quasar absorption systems reported by Rauch et al. [51] and observable by future ultra-stable spectrographs such as ELT-HIRES:

- At $z = 1.6$, corresponding to several metal-line absorption systems in C IV clouds, as listed in Table 2 of Rauch et al. [51] for the QSO HE 1104–1805:

$$\left.\frac{dz}{dt_0}\right|_{z=1.6} \approx -1.727 \times 10^{-10} \text{ yr}^{-1}, \dot{z}c \approx -5.18 \text{ cm/s yr}^{-1}. \quad (52)$$

- At $z = 2.75$, associated with C IV absorption systems observed in Table 1 of Rauch et al. [51] for the QSO Q1422+231:

$$\left.\frac{dz}{dt_0}\right|_{z=2.75} \approx -2.542 \times 10^{-10} \text{ yr}^{-1}, \dot{z}c \approx -7.62 \text{ cm/s yr}^{-1}. \quad (53)$$

- At the point of inversion, near $z = 7.05$, the drift changes sign:

$$\left.\frac{dz}{dt_0}\right|_{z=7.05} \approx +1.688 \times 10^{-12} \text{ yr}^{-1}, \dot{z}c \approx +0.05 \text{ cm/s yr}^{-1}. \quad (54)$$

This last result is a distinct prediction of the rotational model: a *positive redshift drift* at high z that does not arise from metric acceleration but from a purely kinematic phase of increasing angular velocity (see Fig. 2). Future measurements targeting absorption systems in the $2 \lesssim z \lesssim 7$ range—particularly those observable by the ELT—may distinguish between the competing predictions of decelerating rotational models and accelerating metric expansion in Λ CDM.

However, it is important to note that redshift drift measurements at $z \sim 7$ are likely beyond the current technical capabilities of the ELT. While the ELT will be able to detect and resolve high-redshift sources, its spectroscopic stability and signal-to-noise performance are optimized for the $2 \lesssim z \lesssim 5$ regime. At higher redshifts, the scarcity of suitable absorption systems, combined with the need for sub-centimeter-per-second precision over decadal timescales, poses a major observational challenge. As such, observational efforts to test the positive-drift prediction of this model should prioritize well-characterized absorbers in the more accessible intermediate-redshift window.

Although the model is axially symmetric, the observer’s projection of transverse motion varies with angular position on the sky. As a result, sources at the same redshift but located at different directions may exhibit slightly different drift values. This subtle anisotropy in \dot{z} , absent in standard cosmology, constitutes a novel and potentially observable feature of the underlying cosmic rotation.

VII. VALIDATION, LIMITS OF THE MODEL AND DISCUSSION

Within this rotational framework, we obtain a self-consistent angular velocity field $\Omega(r, t)$ analogous to the Hubble–Lemaître relation, directly governing observables such as redshift and its temporal drift. Under the dust-like approximation, the model predicts effective negative pressure, epoch and scale-dependent accelerations, and naturally reinterprets the cosmological constant as a dispersive constant of rotational coherent modes. Although relativistic corrections are not included—implying limited applicability to extremely small scales or intense gravitational fields—the model maintains internal coherence, ensures subluminal velocities, and exhibits a well-defined causal structure. The obtained solutions are separable in cylindrical coordinates, display coherent oscillatory behavior, and enable meaningful comparisons with standard cosmological scenarios and observations.

The following discussion summarizes key results, addresses the observational compatibility and limitations

of the model, and outlines potential avenues for future investigations:

Key findings and features of the model include:

- **Redshift and the Hubble Tension from Rotational Kinematics.**

In this model Redshift encodes both light-travel time and transverse velocity, redefining cosmological horizons as causally connected regions. The observed isotropy of the CMB, typically attributed to inflation, emerges here from long-range inertial coherence: the CMB lies within the apparent horizon defined by the light-travel distance $r = cT_f$, with $T_f = 15.27$ Gyr. Since the redshift function $z(t)$ reaches a finite maximum—governed by the interplay between travel time and rotation—the observable redshift range becomes time-dependent: earlier observers would not access the same ceiling. Transverse velocities grow with redshift, asymptotically approaching c ; for instance, $v_{\perp} \approx 0.99995c$ at $z = 100$ and $0.999999c$ at $z = 650$. As a result, distances inferred from redshift saturate at a maximum radius $r_{\max} \sim 3830$ Mpc, corresponding to an apparent horizon (see Fig. 5) set by the causal structure of relativistic rotation at considered time.

This saturation is not a limitation, but a physical feature of the model. The $z \leftrightarrow r$ relation evolves with cosmic time: photons with identical redshift may originate from slightly different emission radii, depending on the time-dependent evolution of $\Omega(r, t)$. Conversely, sources located at the same radial distance but emitting at slightly different cosmic times may yield different redshifts. This breaks the one-to-one correspondence assumed in standard cosmology and introduces significant degeneracies near the saturation regime, where $v_{\perp} \rightarrow c$. As a result, standard inference methods—based on redshift alone—may yield inconsistent angular sizes or luminosity distances for distant sources, depending on which emission time is implicitly assumed. This ambiguity leads to falsifiable deviations from the predictions of Λ CDM, especially in high- z regimes where the mapping $z(r, t)$ becomes multi-valued.

The Hubble parameter acquires a kinematic interpretation as the local projection of $\Omega(r, t)$, which varies both temporally and spatially. Initially higher near the origin and lower near the horizon, Ω creates a spatial gradient that mimics accelerated expansion at late times, even though its global behavior is governed by monotonic decay due to dispersive attenuation. As cosmological probes sample different epochs—Type Ia Supernovae (low z), DESI BAO (intermediate z), and Planck CMB (high z)—they naturally probe distinct regions of

the evolving field $\Omega(r, t)$. The resulting variation in inferred H_0 values (e.g., 70.39 ± 2.0 , $68.4_{-0.8}^{+1.0}$, and 67.4 ± 0.5) reflects not observational bias, but genuine epoch-dependent kinematics—a natural prediction of the rotational framework.

- **CDP, Coherence Radius, and Cosmological Isotropy.**

The model provides a unified description of gravitational and dark-sector phenomena by reinterpreting the cosmological constant Λ as a cosmological dispersion parameter (CDP). This parameter governs the spatial dispersion of collective rotational modes, with the angular velocity field $\Omega(r, t)$ shaped by the Bessel function $J_1(kr)$. The first zero of this function defines the *coherence radius*, $r_c \approx 3.64 \times 10^{26}$ m, beyond which phase alignment is lost. Although the associated group velocity $v_g \approx 3.05 \times 10^8$ m/s exceeds the speed of light, this reflects the non-causal nature of inertial modes and does not imply any superluminal signal propagation. Instead, v_g defines the extent of coherent rotational structure. Since r_c exceeds the apparent horizon radius $r_U \sim 1.44 \times 10^{26}$ m, all regions of observational interest lie within a single coherence domain. In this regime, the rotation axis becomes observationally ambiguous: as shown in Sec. V, co-rotating observers experience identical inertial dynamics and perceive themselves at the rotational center. Isotropy then emerges not from metric symmetry, as in standard cosmology, but from the solenoidal coherence of the velocity field and the dynamical cancellation of Coriolis-type forces by the associated gravitomagnetic field. Notably, around the present radius r_U , recession velocities reach or slightly exceed c , creating a narrow observational gap. This *transluminal shell* separates nearby luminous sources from more distant regions that remain observable in the future due to the decay of $\Omega(r, t)$ beyond r_U .

- **Inertial Acceleration, Weak-Field Dynamics, and Apparent Dark Matter.**

In the proposed framework, both gravity and coherent cosmic vorticity act as restorative mechanisms that sustain oscillatory modes below the coherence radius during the present cosmological epoch. On intermediate and galactic scales, the resulting acceleration remains below $\lesssim 10^{-10}$ m/s², consistent with the External Field Effect (EFE) [44] and aligned with the empirical Radial Acceleration Relation (RAR) [50]. While such regimes are often interpreted as indicative of a breakdown of Newtonian dynamics or a violation of the SEP, it is important to recall that the SEP is inherently a local principle. The present model does not contradict it, but rather reinterprets the emergence of weak accelerations as a natural consequence of global inertial dy-

namics within a rotating baryonic fluid. This global regulation of local inertial behavior—mediated by the large-scale structure of the vorticity field, in analogy with the gravitomagnetic formulation of Ampère’s law in GEM—resonates with the spirit of Mach’s principle, suggesting that what we perceive as inertial motion is dynamically conditioned by the cosmic distribution of mass in motion, while the local form of physical laws remains unchanged.

• **Redshift Drift as an Observational Probe of Rotation.**

A novel observational signature predicted by this model is the redshift drift, arising directly from the time evolution of $\Omega(r, t)$. While most predictions at high redshift yield a negative drift—consistent with the long-term decay of cosmic rotation—a distinctive feature is a brief *positive drift*, with $\dot{z} \approx +1.688 \times 10^{-12} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (or $\dot{z} c \approx +0.05 \text{ cm/s/yr}$) near $z = 7.05$, at large distances in the early Universe, occurring precisely when $\partial_t \Omega > 0$. This behavior is not expected in standard cosmology. As the Universe evolves and Ω begins to decay, the drift turns negative: for instance, a source at $z = 1.6$ shows a drift of $\dot{z} \approx -1.727 \times 10^{-10} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (or $\dot{z} c \approx -5.18 \text{ cm/s/yr}$), while at $z = 2.75$ the drift is $\dot{z} \approx -2.542 \times 10^{-10} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (or $\dot{z} c \approx -7.62 \text{ cm/s/yr}$). These values lie within the sensitivity range of next-generation ultra-stable spectrographs such as ANDES on the ELT. *Furthermore, the model predicts a mild angular dependence of \dot{z} due to the observer’s projection of transverse motion, offering another potential observational test.* This angular modu-

lation arises because the observed transverse velocity depends on the projection of the cosmic rotation field relative to the observer’s line of sight. It vanishes along the rotation axis and reaches a maximum in the equatorial plane, implying that sources at the same radial distance but located at different angular positions may exhibit slightly different redshift drift values.

Future developments will extend the model to non-uniform density distributions and alternative symmetry classes, aiming to refine predictions for structure formation and improve testability at cosmological scales. Particular attention will be given to mid-redshift BAO constraints and redshift drift measurements, which offer promising opportunities for observational validation of the rotational framework. **In parallel, an independent study already underway focuses on the dark matter paradigm itself**, investigating how local effects of cosmic vorticity may account for apparent mass discrepancies in galaxies without the need for non-baryonic components. In this context, the rotational approach could provide a new perspective for interpreting galactic dynamics and gravitational lensing phenomena.

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